

Yoga Education for Holistic Development of the Self

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ABSTRACT : In India, the long tradition of spirituality has retained its position that is manifested in customs, rituals, prayer, worship and so on. However, with the increasing difficulties of the modern age, the practices have been inflicted. Education system has also been affected with great casualty. Hence, there is a need to implement strategies for developing holistic perspective and Yoga is the best measure in this regard.

Keywords : Holistic Development, Yoga Education, Self

Introduction

The modern education system is rooted in materialism and aimed at fulfilling economic and social needs of today's culture. Contemporary researches in various fields agree that all human endeavours are guided by two distinct worldviews namely material and spiritual. The indigenous spiritual worldview of India can be understood with reference to the descriptions of holistic paradigm. The holistic worldview is essentially spiritual worldview and the primary defining characteristic of all holistic educators is their profound respect for a spontaneous

creative life force or energy that manifests the ultimate reality of the universe. In the ordinary sense, things seem to be relatively independent but in some way enfolded into everything. In spite of external separateness, conflict and competition there is an underlying bond merging everything in the universe. Holistic paradigm envisages the physical, mental, emotional and spiritual features, their interactions and nurturance. It casts aside the so-called inflicting industrialisation with the careful nurturing and by means of sustainable development. Holistic development refers to the all-round development of a person giving due recognition to physical,

emotional, cognitive, interpersonal, spiritual, social and moral aspects of human nature.

Emergence and Evolution of Yoga: Yoga, derived from the Sanskrit word 'Yuj' meaning 'to unite', refers to the psycho-physiological discipline, which aims body-mind harmony. The practice of Yoga implies practice of some techniques or procedures to regulate body and mind. Again, in its broader connotation, Yoga implies a way of life that strives for holistic development. Yoga in earlier times was regarded as a science of consciousness. Later on, it became the science of possibilities dealing with the crucial problems of human life. Today, it is being observed as a holistic approach with potential refinement of most of the latent aspects of human life. Yoga system was developed and put to practice by the ancient Indian sages to support the emergence of transcendental state. Patanjali and other ancestors of Yoga were experts in making a harmonious way of living with oneself along with the environment. In Vedic literature, especially *Kathopanishad* envisages that Yoga is a system of holistic life where all the domains of human life receive due attention. In Veda-Vyasa's *Bhagawad-Gita*, the practical aspects of Yoga in real life situations had been woven comprehensively. In modern times, Yoga is meant for personality development, transformation of consciousness and integration within the self leading to the holistic well-being. Sri Aurobindo puts Yoga as the methodical effort towards self-perfection keeping aside the limitations and imperfections in man resulting into an all-round personality development. Krishnamurti considers Yoga as a state of choice less awareness. In the 1980s, Yoga became popular as a system of physical exercise across

the Western world. Yoga gurus from India like Baba Ramdev introduced Yoga to the West, following the success path of Swami Vivekananda in the late 19th and early 20th century. Now, Yoga became more popular in schools through physical education classes or Yoga in schools or after-school Fitness Programs. Every age group of people are getting benefits of Yoga and enjoying this art with happiness.

Yoga leads to a set of practices that include various procedures-

- Physical (*asana*)
- Physiological (*pranayama*) and
- Psychological (*yama, niyama; dharana, dhyana; bhakti, prapatti; shravana, manana; and nidhidhyasana, viveka and vichara*).

Such practices aim at developing right attitudes and values, conduct and discipline, virtues and strengths, aptitudes and abilities, interpersonal relations and ultimately awareness of the spiritual realisation of the transcendent self that is the goal of holistic development.

Yoga Education: Yoga education implies the training/teaching process of Yoga but recently it is seen as the application of Yogic practices to provide better support to the educational process for enhancing human personality. The thinkers in today's educational system are opting for the inclusion of Yoga for improving the quality of education. It is observed that the traditional Indian values which emphasized the four Noble Aims (*PurusarthaChatustaya*) viz., Ethics (*Dharma*), Earning (*Artha*), Enjoyment (*Kama*), and Emancipation (*Moksha*) are equally relevant even today. The education

system should strive for moral (*Dharma*), socio-economic (*Artha*), psychological (*Kama*), and spiritual (*Moksha*) values. Yoga education leads to self-awareness. Modern world is passing through a war like situation where people are indulged in a rat race losing their own existence. Significantly, the education system provides no training to develop an awareness of the self. There is a crucial need to learn and understand the subtle realities of the self-existence that is possible only through Yoga education. Yoga can provide training for the development of self-awareness, about the realities of our being and becoming. In the *Tattiriyopanisad* following the instructions of Varuna, Bhrigu goes through the actualisation process of the five Sheaths (*PanchaKosha*) i.e., Corporeal Sheath (*AnnamayaKosha*), Vital Sheath (*PranamayaKosha*), Mental Sheath (*ManomayaKosha*), Gnostic Sheath (*VijnanamayaKosha*) and Beatific Sheath (*AnandamayaKosha*) successfully and attains self-realisation. Human consciousness involves different dimensions- biological, emotional, mental, intuitive-psychical and spiritual based on the descriptions of five Sheaths (*PanchaKosha*) in Taittiriya Upanishad. In modern times, human consciousness is restricted to the first three koshas and the last two are marginalised. The Indian tradition observes that much of human sufferings are due to such a limited view of self-definition.

Yoga education generally leads to the development of general awareness, promotion of uniqueness, creative consciousness, promotion of will power, management of mental health and many more. Studies have shown that Yoga contributes to flexibility and muscular fitness. In addition, Yoga helps in coping up with the

concerns related to the process of growing up. It counters stresses and strains. Also it helps in reducing the stress. Both Yoga and physical education are seen as routes for achieving overall development of children. Due to the reasons mentioned above, both Yoga and physical education have to be given the due importance in the school education.

Inclusion of Yoga in Schools: It is obvious that the Yogic practices need to be included in daily basis in all educational institutions from elementary to higher education. Opinions may be sought from the experts if needed regarding orientation of Yoga education that can lead our young generations on the right track of self-realisation. Practice of Yoga should be made mandatory for the teachers, administrators and policy makers in this regard. This indigenous system must be revived to attain the glory of classical Indian tradition and to enrich our culture through education. Yoga can contribute to the quality of school education in general and to health and physical development in particular. This Yoga scheme, therefore, focuses on preparing trained teachers for Yoga education and training in Indian schools. Regular practice of the Yoga provides outer and inner relief by keeping away from the countless ailments at the physical and mental level. Practicing *asanas* strengthens the body and mind as well as creates the feeling of well being. The feeling of well-being creates facilitating nature within us and thus enhances the social well-being. Improved concentration level helps in meditating and provides calming effect and inner peace to the mind. Yoga is like a practical philosophy that develops self-discipline and self awareness within us through regular practice. The physical and physiological aspects of Yoga like *asana* and

pranayama can be incorporated at a convenient hour. These are capable of building high capacity for self-regulation and proper functioning of the body. *Pranayama*, in addition contributes to focused attention and increased concentration much desired for any successful learning process. Again, it reduces stress, emotional turmoil and maintains emotional balance.

As per the National Curriculum Framework (NCF)-2005, Yoga is an integral part of Health and Physical Education at all levels of school education. The following is the summary of the stipulations made in the National Curriculum Framework - 2005 (prepared by NCERT) and the Position Paper on Health and Physical Education:

1. The precondition for all development is healthy physical growth of all children. This requires that the basic needs in terms of adequate nutrition, physical exercise and other psycho-social needs are addressed. Participation of all children in free play, informal and formal games, yoga and sports activities is essential for their physical and psycho-social development. The range of abilities as a result of games, sports and yoga will improve stamina, fine and gross motor skills and dexterities, self-awareness and control, and coordination in team games. Simple adaptation of playgrounds, equipment and rules can make activities and games accessible to all children in the school. Children can achieve high levels of excellence in sports, athletics, gymnastics, yoga and performing arts such as dance. When the emphasis shifts from enjoyment to achievement, such training can make demands of discipline and practice that can create stress at this stage. Whereas all students must be involved in health and physical education activities, those who choose to excel in games and sports need to be provided adequate opportunities.
2. This curricular area adopts a holistic definition of health within which physical education and yoga contribute to the physical, social, emotional and mental development of a child.
3. The entire group (Health and Physical Education and yoga) must be taken together as a comprehensive health and physical education curriculum, replacing the fragmentary approach current in schools today. As a core part of the curriculum, time allocated for games and for yoga must not be reduced, under any circumstances.
4. Recognizing this subject as a core subject, Health and Physical Education must continue to be a compulsory subject from the primary to the secondary stages and as an optional subject at higher secondary stage. However, it needs to be given equal status with other subjects, a status that is not being given at present.
5. In order to transact the curriculum effectively, it is essential to ensure that the minimum essential physical space and equipments are available in every school. Teacher preparation for this area needs well planned and concerted

efforts. This subject area consisting of health education, physical education and yoga must be suitably integrated into the elementary and secondary pre-service teacher education courses. The potential of the existing physical education training institutes should be reviewed and utilized adequately. Similarly, their appropriate syllabi and teacher training for transaction of yoga in schools need to be reviewed and reformulated.

6. Yoga could be introduced from the primary level onwards in informal ways, but formal introduction of yogic exercises should begin only from class sixth onwards. All interventions including even health and hygiene education must rely on the practical and experiential dimensions of children's lives.

Recent Trends and Practices in Yoga Education: Education, being a subject in the Concurrent List of the Constitution, and the majority of schools being under the jurisdiction of the State Governments, it is for the respective State/ Union Territory Governments to introduce this subject in their schools. However, for the schools affiliated to Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE), Health and Physical Education is compulsory for Classes I to X and optional at classes XI and XII. Based on the NCF-2005, the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) have already developed model syllabi and textual material for Health and Physical Education, which includes Yoga. The Ministry of AYUSH at present has

constituted National Board for the Promotion and Development of Yoga and Naturopathy. As part of the celebration of the International Day of Yoga-2016, it has been decided to organize Yoga Olympiad, involving school children. In order to promote Yoga among students, CBSE also organizes National level competition annually for the schools affiliated to it. A committee was constituted by the Government on 15th January, 2016 on yoga education in universities under the chairpersonship of Prof H.R. Nagendra, Chancellor, Swami Vivekananda Yoga Anusandhana, Samsthana, Bengaluru. The Terms of Reference of the committee included identification of courses and programmes in yogic art and science and the level at which it can be offered; to determine the eligibility qualifications for students for joining yoga education programme at different levels; to prescribe recommendations for qualifications for faculty of yoga etc. The Committee has submitted its report on 19th April 2016. It has recommended seven programmes for implementation in universities viz. (i) Certificate Course in Yoga (CCY) of 6 to 12 months duration; (ii) Bachelors of Science (Yoga)-BSc.(Yoga) of 3 to 6 years; (iii) Post Graduate Diploma in Yoga (PGDY) of 1 to 2 years; (iv) Post Graduate Diploma in Yoga Therapy (PGDYT) of 1 to 2 years; (v) Masters of Science (MSc.)- Yoga of 2 years to 4 years; (vi) Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.)-Yoga of 3 to 5 years; and (vii) Doctor of Philosophy (Integrated)- Yoga of 4 to 6 years. The committee has also prescribed the qualifications for faculty of yoga. The committee has made other recommendations for promotion of yoga in universities. Recently in the Uniform Curriculum

Structure for Two-Year B.Ed. Programme in West Bengal following NCTE Regulations, 2014 the implementation of the traditional practice of yoga has been included through a core paper *Understanding the Self (Course: EPC-4)*. The prime objective is to prepare the prospective teachers with the indigenous system of Yoga and to make an awareness of the interrelationship of yoga and well-being. In the Revised M.Ed. syllabus (w.e.f. 2015-17) of Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah, a pioneering institute of Teacher Education has included *Self Development through Yoga (Course: 2.1.6)* so that the approaching teacher-educators be accustomed with the contribution of yogic practices in coping with the daily life situations. In West Bengal, the Ramakrishna Mission Vivekananda University, University of Burdwan, Jadavpur University, Visva-Bharati University, Netaji Subhas Open University and Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira conduct Post-Graduate Diploma Course in Yoga to be at par with the need of the situation and to create professionals in the field of Yoga who can address the challenges of time and meet the demands of the society. Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga, New Delhi; Bihar School of Yoga, Munger, Krishnamacharya Yoga Mandiram, Chennai; The Yoga Institute, Santacruz, Mumbai conduct Teacher Training Course for Yoga. Swami Vivekananda Yoga Anusandhana Samsthana, Bengaluru is a deemed university and conducts various courses on Yoga including Ph.D. On 11th December 2014, The United Nations General Assembly has declared “**International Day of Yoga**” to be celebrated on “**21st June**” every year in the world.

Conclusion

Yoga is the practice or art of accessing and integrating all aspects of our **Mind, body, and soul** — in the pursuit of Inner Harmony and Physical Health. Hence, we should not lose our track from this rich heritage of India. Here are some suggestions to attain the best possible outcome of Yoga for different stake holders—

- The main motif of yoga is to restrain the mind stuff from taking various forms (Patanjali). It is not confined to some *asanas* or postures and an inevitable remedy of today’s fragmented world scenario.
- The government should take proper care of nurturing this indigenous system in its apposite sense and spirit through different institutions formally and informally.
- The universities and higher education institutions across the country should definitely conduct Undergraduate, Post Graduate and Ph.D. courses in Yoga to inculcate the classical Indian tradition at the optimum level.
- The administrators, policy makers and governing bodies while recruiting faculties especially for Physical Education and also for other disciplines should give priority to those having an orientation course in Yoga.

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